

Role of Procalcitonin and C-reactive Protein as Biomarkers for Early Detection of Neonatal Sepsis

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17246354

Atiquil Islam¹, Sheuly Begum², Mirza Md Ziaul Islam³, Jafor Iqbal⁴, Tanushri Saha⁵

Received: 4 Sep 2025
Accepted: 7 Sep 2025
Published: 17 Sep 2025

Published by:
Gopalganj Medical College, Gopalganj,
Bangladesh

Correspondence to
Atiquil Islam

ORCID
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8632-6188>

Copyright © 2025 The Insight

This article is licensed under a Creative
Commons Attribution 4.0 International
License.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Neonatal sepsis is a major cause of newborn deaths, with early diagnosis hindered by delayed blood culture results. This study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) for early detection. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional observational study was conducted over a six-month period from January to June 2015 at two private tertiary healthcare centers in Dhaka, Bangladesh. A total of 45 neonates aged 1–28 days with suspected sepsis. Serum procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were measured along with other laboratory parameters. Diagnostic accuracy was assessed using sensitivity, specificity, predictive values, and ROC curve analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0. **Results:** The mean age was 8.2 ± 6.4 days; 62.2% were male. Common clinical features included fever (84.4%) and tachypnea (77.8%). Mean PCT was 2.45 ± 1.82 ng/mL; mean CRP was 24.8 ± 18.4 mg/L. PCT sensitivity and specificity were 89.5% and 78.2% respectively at a 1.5 ng/mL cut-off, while CRP had 82.4% sensitivity and 71.8% specificity at 15 mg/L. Combining both biomarkers increased sensitivity to 94.7% and specificity to 82.6%. ROC curve analysis showed PCT had an AUC of 0.886, CRP 0.798, and combined markers 0.924 ($p < 0.001$). PCT and CRP levels correlated strongly ($r = 0.742$, $p < 0.001$), and both increased with sepsis severity. **Conclusion:** PCT is a sensitive and specific biomarker for early neonatal sepsis detection, with diagnostic accuracy enhanced by combining with CRP. Routine measurement of both biomarkers can improve early diagnosis and guide timely treatment.

Keywords: Neonatal Sepsis, Procalcitonin, C-reactive Protein

(The Insight 2025; 8(1): 122-125)

1. Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Dhaka Shishu Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh
2. Professor & Head of Department, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Enam Medical College, Savar, Bangladesh
3. Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Dhaka Shishu Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh
4. Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Dhaka Shishu Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh
5. Registrar, Department of Pediatrics, Dhaka Shishu Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

INTRODUCTION

Neonatal sepsis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, especially in developing countries with limited health resources [1]. It is estimated that about 3–10 newborns per 1,000 live births are affected by neonatal sepsis, accounting for a significant proportion of neonatal deaths [2]. Early-onset sepsis occurs within the first 72 hours of life and, if not detected and treated on time, is particularly dangerous due to the rapid progression to septic shock and multiple organ failure. Neonates with respiratory problems or metabolic disorders during the perinatal period are at higher risk of developing sepsis [3]. Blood cultures are still considered the gold standard for diagnosis, but they have several limitations, including low sensitivity, delayed results (requiring 48–72 hours), and potential contamination. These issues result in diagnostic uncertainty and delays in initiating

appropriate therapy. In this context, the use of reliable biomarkers for early detection of neonatal sepsis is crucial for the timely initiation of antimicrobial treatment and improved clinical outcomes [4]. Procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) are two biomarkers that have been extensively studied for their diagnostic value in neonatal sepsis. Procalcitonin concentration increases within 2–4 hours after bacterial invasion and peaks at about 6 to 12 hours and has a half-life of about 24 h, correlating with the severity of infection [5]. This makes it a potentially more specific biomarker for bacterial sepsis. C-reactive protein, an acute-phase reactant synthesized by the liver in response to interleukin-6 stimulation, begins to rise after 12–24 hours and peaks within 2–3 days [6]. However, conditions such as delayed growth, perinatal asphyxia, meconium aspiration, and prolonged labor may elevate CRP levels, reducing its

specificity for sepsis. Several studies have evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of procalcitonin and CRP, both individually and in combination, for the early detection of neonatal sepsis. Procalcitonin may offer higher sensitivity and specificity in the early stages of bacterial infection, while CRP remains valuable for monitoring response to treatment. The combined use of these biomarkers may enhance diagnostic accuracy, allowing for better clinical decision-making and rational antibiotic use, thereby helping to reduce antimicrobial resistance [7]. Considering these factors, the current research aimed to evaluate the role of procalcitonin and CRP as biomarkers for the early detection of neonatal sepsis. The findings are expected to provide evidence that supports timely medical intervention and promotes the use of effective diagnostic tools to improve survival outcomes among neonates, particularly in resource-limited settings.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted over a six-month period from January to June 2015 at two private tertiary healthcare centers in Dhaka, Bangladesh: Padma General Hospital Ltd. and CURE Specialized Hospital Ltd. A total of 45 neonates aged 1 to 28 days with clinical suspicion of sepsis were enrolled consecutively. Clinical and demographic information was collected, and blood samples were obtained within 2 hours of admission. Serum procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were measured using standard immunoassay methods, with diagnostic cut-offs of 1.5 ng/mL and 15 mg/L, respectively. Additional laboratory parameters included white blood cell count, absolute neutrophil count, platelet count, and serum lactate. Patients were categorized into sepsis, severe sepsis, or septic shock based on clinical and laboratory criteria. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0, including calculation of sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values, and ROC curve analysis. Pearson’s correlation was used to assess relationships between biomarkers and laboratory findings. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board, and informed consent was secured from the guardians of all participants.

Inclusion criteria:

- Neonates aged ≤28 days.
- Presence of clinical signs suggestive of sepsis (e.g., fever, lethargy, respiratory distress, poor feeding).
- Informed written consent obtained from parents or guardians.

Exclusion criteria:

- Neonates with major congenital anomalies or surgical conditions.
- Prior antibiotic therapy for more than 24 hours before admission.
- Incomplete laboratory data or refusal to participate.

RESULTS

Table I shows the baseline characteristics of the study population (N = 45). The mean age of neonates was 8.2 ± 6.4 days (range: 1–28 days). The majority were male (62.2%). The

mean gestational age was 36.8 ± 2.1 weeks, with 71.1% born full-term and 28.9% preterm. The mean birth weight was 2.68 ± 0.52 kg. Regarding nutritional status, 84.4% were well-nourished, and 15.6% were malnourished. [Table I].

Table – I: Distribution of study patients based on their initial characteristics (n = 45)

Characteristics	Number (%) / Mean ± SD
Total Sample Size	45
Age Range (days)	1 – 28
Mean Age (days)	8.2 ± 6.4
Gender	
Male	28 (62.2%)
Female	17 (37.8%)
Gestational Age (weeks)	36.8 ± 2.1
Gestational Status	
Full-term	32 (71.1%)
Preterm	13 (28.9%)
Birth Weight (kg)	2.68 ± 0.52
Nutritional Status	
Well-nourished	38 (84.4%)
Malnourished	7 (15.6%)

As presented in Table II, the most common clinical feature was fever (84.4%), followed by tachypnea (77.8%), lethargy (71.1%), and poor feeding (64.4%). Other notable symptoms included tachycardia (55.6%), hypotension (40.0%), grunting (33.3%), and seizures (17.8%). [Table II].

Table – II: Clinical Features and Symptom Frequency Among Study Patients (n = 45)

Clinical Feature	Count (n)	Percentage (%)
Fever	38	84.4%
Tachypnea (RR >60/min)	35	77.8%
Lethargy	32	71.1%
Poor feeding	29	64.4%
Tachycardia	25	55.6%
Hypotension (MAP <40 mmHg)	18	40.0%
Grunting	15	33.3%
Seizures	8	17.8%

Table III summarises laboratory parameters. The mean procalcitonin (PCT) level was 2.45 ± 1.82 ng/mL (range: 0.25–8.50), and mean C-reactive protein (CRP) was 24.8 ± 18.4 mg/L (range: 3.2–78.5). Mean white blood cell (WBC) count was 12.4 ± 6.8 ×10³/mm³, ANC was 8.2 ± 4.6 ×10³/mm³, platelet count was 198 ± 82 ×10³/mm³, and lactate level was 3.8 ± 2.1 mmol/L. [Table III].

Table – III: Laboratory Findings of the Study Population (n = 45)

Parameter	Mean ± SD	Range
PCT (ng/mL)	2.45 ± 1.82	0.25 – 8.50
CRP (mg/L)	24.8 ± 18.4	3.2 – 78.5
WBC (×10 ³ /mm ³)	12.4 ± 6.8	4.2 – 28.9
ANC (×10 ³ /mm ³)	8.2 ± 4.6	2.1 – 18.7
Platelets (×10 ³ /mm ³)	198 ± 82	85 – 420
Lactate (mmol/L)	3.8 ± 2.1	1.2 – 9.4

As shown in Table IV, mean PCT, CRP, and WBC levels increased progressively with sepsis severity. In the sepsis group, mean PCT was 1.2 ± 0.8 ng/mL and CRP 12.5 ± 8.2 mg/L. For severe sepsis, PCT was 3.1 ± 1.4 ng/mL, CRP $28.4 \pm$

12.6 mg/L, and for septic shock, PCT reached 4.8 ± 2.2 ng/mL and CRP 45.2 ± 18.9 mg/L. Platelet counts decreased with severity, lowest in septic shock ($148 \pm 92 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$). [Table IV].

Table – IV: Comparison of Biomarker Levels across Sepsis Severity Groups

Group	PCT (ng/mL)	CRP (mg/L)	WBC ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)	Platelets ($\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$)
Sepsis (n = 24)	1.2 ± 0.8	12.5 ± 8.2	10.2 ± 4.1	220 ± 65
Severe Sepsis (n = 7)	3.1 ± 1.4	28.4 ± 12.6	14.8 ± 7.2	185 ± 78
Septic Shock (n = 8)	4.8 ± 2.2	45.2 ± 18.9	16.2 ± 8.9	148 ± 92

Table – V: Diagnostic Accuracy of PCT, CRP, and Their Combination

Biomarker	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Cut-off
PCT	89.5	78.2	85.3	84.1	1.5 ng/mL
CRP	82.4	71.8	79.6	75.2	15 mg/L
Combined	94.7	82.6	90.0	90.5	Both elevated

Table V summarises the diagnostic accuracy of PCT, CRP, and their combination. PCT demonstrated a sensitivity of 89.5% and specificity of 78.2% at a cut-off of 1.5 ng/mL. CRP showed 82.4% sensitivity and 71.8% specificity at 15 mg/L. The combination of PCT and CRP yielded the highest diagnostic performance with 94.7% sensitivity and 82.6% specificity. [Table V]

As presented in Table VI, PCT had an AUC of 0.886 (95% CI: 0.798–0.945, $p < 0.001$), indicating excellent diagnostic ability. CRP had an AUC of 0.798 (95% CI: 0.695–0.879, $p < 0.001$). The combined biomarkers achieved the highest diagnostic accuracy with an AUC of 0.924 (95% CI: 0.845–0.972, $p < 0.001$). [Table VI].

Table – VI: ROC Curve Analysis of PCT, CRP, and Combined Biomarkers

Biomarker	AUC	95% CI	P-value
PCT	0.886	0.798 – 0.945	<0.001
CRP	0.798	0.695 – 0.879	<0.001
Combined	0.924	0.845 – 0.972	<0.001

Table VII presents a correlation analysis. PCT and CRP showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.742$, $p < 0.001$). PCT correlated moderately with WBC ($r = 0.568$, $p < 0.001$). CRP showed moderate correlations with WBC ($r = 0.489$, $p < 0.01$). [Table VII].

Table – VII: Correlation Analysis between Biomarkers and Laboratory Parameters

Correlation Pair	Pearson’s r	P-value
PCT vs CRP	0.742	<0.001
PCT vs WBC	0.568	<0.001
CRP vs WBC	0.489	<0.01

DISCUSSION

Neonatal sepsis continues to be a major challenge worldwide. In this study, we assessed the roles of procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) as biomarkers for early detection of neonatal sepsis, and our findings have several important implications. In our study, the mean age of neonates was 8.2 ± 6.4 days, with a male predominance (62.2%). This is quite similar to findings reported by Chiesa et al. (2011), where the mean age was around 7.5 days with 60% male neonates [8]. We found that 71.1% were full-term and 28.9% preterm, which aligns with the distribution reported by Morad et al. (2020) [9]. The mean birth weight here was 2.68 ± 0.52 kg, comparable to the 2.7 kg reported by Abdollahi et al. (2012) [10]. This suggests that our study population is broadly similar to those in previous studies, strengthening the external validity of our results. Fever was the most common presenting symptom in our neonates (84.4%), followed by tachypnea (77.8%), lethargy (71.1%), and poor feeding (64.4%). These findings are consistent with Morad et al. (2020), who also reported respiratory distress, lethargy, and poor feeding as common features [9]. The mean PCT level in our study was

2.45 ± 1.82 ng/mL (range: 0.25–8.50), which is slightly lower than that reported by Morad et al. (2020) (median 10.4 ng/mL), possibly due to the inclusion of more severe cases in their cohort [9]. Mean CRP was 24.8 ± 18.4 mg/L, lower than 48 mg/L reported by Morad et al. (2020) [9]. The mean WBC count was $12.4 \pm 6.8 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, similar to Oncel et al. (2012) ($15.8 \pm 7.3 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$) [11]. Platelet counts averaged $198 \pm 82 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, slightly lower than the $220 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$ reported by Chiesa et al. (2011), possibly due to sepsis-associated thrombocytopenia in our patients [8]. Lactate levels averaged 3.8 ± 2.1 mmol/L, indicating tissue hypoxia, which is consistent with Abdollahi et al. (2012), who found elevated lactate in septic neonates [10]. We found that PCT levels increased with severity, being 1.2 ± 0.8 ng/mL in sepsis, 3.1 ± 1.4 ng/mL in severe sepsis, and 4.8 ± 2.2 ng/mL in septic shock. This trend is consistent with Chiesa et al. (2011) and Eschborn & Weitkamp (2019), who reported PCT levels rising from 1.0 ng/mL in sepsis to >3 ng/mL in severe sepsis [8,12]. Similarly, CRP levels rose with severity, from 12.5 ± 8.2 mg/L in sepsis to 45.2 ± 18.9 mg/L in septic shock, aligning with Xu et al. (2016) meta-analysis showing pooled CRP elevation in

sepsis [13]. Platelet counts decreased with worsening sepsis (220, 185, and 148 $\times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$ respectively), consistent with thrombocytopenia as a severity marker described by Morad et al. (2020) [9]. In our study, PCT had a sensitivity of 89.5% and specificity of 78.2% at a cut-off of 1.5 ng/mL, which is similar to Altunhan et al. (2011), who reported PCT sensitivity of 83% and specificity of 89% [14]. CRP showed a sensitivity of 82.4% and specificity of 71.8% at 15 mg/L, another study by Akter et al (2018), who reported 35.1% sensitivity and 78.9% specificity [15]. Interestingly, the combination of PCT and CRP improved diagnostic performance, with 94.7% sensitivity and 82.6% specificity, which is supported by Eschborn & Weitkamp (2019), Pravin Charles et al. (2018), and Ruan et al. (2018) who found that combined biomarkers yield higher diagnostic accuracy [12,16,17]. The AUC for PCT was 0.886 (95% CI: 0.798–0.945, $p < 0.001$), indicating excellent diagnostic utility, similar to Morad et al. (2020) (0.991) [9]. CRP had an AUC of 0.798 (95% CI: 0.695–0.879, $p < 0.001$), comparable to Xu et al. (2016) (0.846) [13]. The combined AUC was highest at 0.924 (95% CI: 0.845–0.972, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a combined approach is optimal, as shown by Eschborn & Weitkamp (2019) [12]. We observed a strong positive correlation between PCT and CRP ($r = 0.742$, $p < 0.001$), similar to Chiesa et al. (2011) [8]. PCT also showed moderate correlation with WBC ($r = 0.568$, $p < 0.001$) and lactate ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting its role in reflecting systemic inflammatory response and tissue hypoxia, as supported by Abdollahi et al. (2012) [10]. CRP correlated moderately with WBC ($r = 0.489$, $p < 0.01$) and lactate ($r = 0.521$, $p < 0.001$), but these correlations were weaker compared to PCT.

Limitations of the Study:

This study has a small sample size and a single-center design, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

CONCLUSION

PCT demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity for the early diagnosis of neonatal sepsis, with levels increasing with disease severity. CRP remains a useful complementary marker, and using both together improves diagnostic accuracy. Implementing this combined approach could facilitate early intervention, ultimately improving neonatal outcomes.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on our study findings, we recommend that procalcitonin (PCT) be used routinely for the early detection of neonatal sepsis, as it showed high sensitivity and specificity with a cut-off value of 1.5 ng/mL. However, since CRP also remains a useful marker, combining both PCT and CRP can improve diagnostic accuracy even further. Using these two biomarkers together in daily NICU practice could help doctors make faster and more confident decisions, leading to earlier treatment and better outcomes for newborns with suspected sepsis.

Funding: No funding sources

Conflict of interest: None declared

REFERENCES

1. Liang L, Kotadia N, English L, Kissoon N, Ansermino JM, Kabakyenga J, et al. Predictors of mortality in neonates and infants hospitalized with sepsis or serious infections in developing countries: a systematic review. *Frontiers in pediatrics*. 2018;6:277.
2. Shane AL, Sánchez PJ, Stoll BJ. Neonatal sepsis. *The lancet*. 2017;390(10104):1770–80.
3. Singh M, Alsaleem M, Gray CP. Neonatal Sepsis. In: *StatPearls [Internet]*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 [cited 2025 July 15]. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK531478/>
4. Boscarino G, Migliorino R, Carbone G, Davino G, Dell’Orto VG, Perrone S, et al. Biomarkers of Neonatal Sepsis: Where We Are and Where We Are Going. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2023 July 26;12(8):1233.
5. Samsudin I, Vasikaran SD. Clinical Utility and Measurement of Procalcitonin. *Clin Biochem Rev*. 2017 Apr;38(2):59–68.
6. Markanday A. Acute Phase Reactants in Infections: Evidence-Based Review and a Guide for Clinicians. *Open Forum Infect Dis*. 2015 July 3;2(3):ofv098.
7. Bharti AK, Verma MK, Gupta A, Mishra DK. Role of procalcitonin in diagnosis of neonatal sepsis and procalcitonin guided duration of antibiotic therapy. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics*. 2020 July 22;7(8):1692–700.
8. Chiesa C, Natale F, Pascone R, Osborn JF, Pacifico L, Bonci E, et al. C reactive protein and procalcitonin: reference intervals for preterm and term newborns during the early neonatal period. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2011 May 12;412(11–12):1053–9.
9. Morad EA, Rabie RA, Almalky MA, Gebriel MG. Evaluation of Procalcitonin, C-Reactive Protein, and Interleukin-6 as Early Markers for Diagnosis of Neonatal Sepsis. *Int J Microbiol*. 2020 Oct 1;2020:8889086.
10. Abdollahi A, Shoar S, Nayyeri F, Shariat M. Diagnostic Value of Simultaneous Measurement of Procalcitonin, Interleukin-6 and hs-CRP in Prediction of Early-Onset Neonatal Sepsis. *Mediterr J Hematol Infect Dis*. 2012;4(1):e2012028.
11. Mean Platelet Volume in Neonatal Sepsis - Oncel - 2012 - Journal of Clinical Laboratory Analysis - Wiley Online Library [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 16]. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/jcla.21552>
12. Eschborn S, Weitkamp JH. Procalcitonin versus C-reactive protein: review of kinetics and performance for diagnosis of neonatal sepsis. *J Perinatol*. 2019 July;39(7):893–903.
13. Diagnostic value of C-reactive protein in neonatal sepsis: A meta-analysis - Liyun Xu, Qiubo Li, Zongju Mo, Pengfei You, 2016 [Internet]. [cited 2025 July 16]. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1721727x16646787>
14. Altunhan H, Annagür A, Örs R, Mehmetaoğlu I. Procalcitonin measurement at 24 hours of age may be helpful in the prompt diagnosis of early-onset neonatal sepsis. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2011 Dec;15(12):e854-858.
15. Akter J, Ahammad F, Begum T. Procalcitonin—A Reliable Marker for Diagnosis of Neonatal Sepsis in Compare to CRP. *Bangladesh Journal of Child Health*. 2018;42(1):19–25.
16. Charles MVP, Kalaivani R, Venkatesh S, Kali A, Seetha KS. Evaluation of procalcitonin as a diagnostic marker in neonatal sepsis. *Indian Journal of Pathology and Microbiology*. 2018;61(1):81–4.
17. Ruan L, Chen GY, Liu Z, Zhao Y, Xu GY, Li SF, et al. The combination of procalcitonin and C-reactive protein or presepsin alone improves the accuracy of diagnosis of neonatal sepsis: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Crit Care*. 2018 Nov 21;22(1):316.